

CLIMATE CHANGE AND FOOD SECURITY IN PAKISTAN: SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONSEQUENCES AND STRATEGIC POLICY OPTIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE RESILIENCE

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ABSTRACT

Pakistan's food security is being threatened by climate change, which has broad socio-economic ramifications. Millions of people's livelihoods are in jeopardy due to the sharp decline in agricultural output brought on by rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall patterns, and an increase in the frequency of catastrophic weather events like floods and droughts. Therefore, the multifaceted effects of climate change on Pakistan's food supply are addressed in this research, with an emphasis on how these disruptions worsen poverty, inequality, and migration from the countryside to the cities. It draws attention to the vulnerability of small-scale farmers and marginalized communities, who are disproportionately affected by these issues. A thorough framework of policy choices is presented in the research to address these immediate issues. Examples of short-term responses are providing backup food supplies and bolstering catastrophe risk management systems. Diversification of crops, better water resource management, and investments in climate-resilient agricultural innovations are the main themes of medium-term strategies. Whereas, promoting climate-smart agriculture, implementing structural changes to land use regulations, and strengthening regional collaboration to reduce risks and exchange best practices are all necessary for long-term solutions. By putting Pakistan's food security dilemma within the global framework of climate evolution and sustainable development, this research highlights the need for integrated and inclusive planning. It calls for harnessing international climate funds and supporting collaborative efforts to establish a durable, responsible food system for Pakistan's development.

Keywords: Food security, climate change, security dilemma, climate funds.

INTRODUCTION

Introduction to Climate Change

Climate change is mainly a long-term phenomenon that refers to changes in patterns of weather and temperature and substantially contributes to defining the world's global climate.

Such changes in weather and temperature patterns can be natural because of changes in the activity of the sun or huge volcanic eruptions. Adding to these natural factors, from the 1800s, human activities have become a key driving source of

climate change. These human activities include the burning of fossil fuels like coal, gas, and oil (What is Climate change?, 2023).

Fossil fuel combustion releases greenhouse gases into the atmosphere, which encircles the planet like a blanket and traps solar heat, causing temperatures to rise. Moreover, Methane and carbon dioxide are the two primary greenhouse gases responsible for climate change. These result, for instance, from burning coal to heat a building or petrol to operate a vehicle. Carbon dioxide may also be released through land clearing and forest destruction. The two main sectors that emit methane are agriculture, oil and gas activities. Among the primary industries producing greenhouse gases are energy, industry, transportation, buildings, agriculture, and the utilization of land (What is Climate change?, 2023).

Moreover, during the mid-time period of the 20th century, the earth witnessed the evident changes and effects of climate change. A rise in global air and water temperatures, higher sea levels, a long-term, endured, widespread decrease in snow and ice cover, modifications to atmospheric and ocean flow, and regional weather patterns that affect seasonal rainfall conditions are just a few of the changes that have been observed over the past century. The excess heat in the climate system spurred on by greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere is what contributes to these changes. Human activities including the combustion of fossil fuels (coal, oil, and natural gas), logging, agriculture, and changes in land use are the main sources of these extra greenhouse gases (Understanding the big picture, 2023).

The atmosphere gets to hold more "heat-trapping" greenhouse gases as a result of these activities. An enhanced greenhouse effect is consistent with the pattern of changes in the climate system that have been documented. The sun, volcanoes, and other natural variability factors cannot fully account for the time and magnitude of the observed variations in climate. In addition to the emission of these greenhouse gases, natural processes, obliterated by human influence, can also cause climate change. These include external factors like volcanic eruptions, deviations in Earth's orbit, and changes in the amount of energy produced by the

Sun, as well as internal oscillations like cyclical ocean patterns (such as El Niño, La Niña, and the Pacific Decadal Oscillation) (What is Climate Change, 2023).

Effects of Climate Change

Climate change, without a doubt, has become the world's biggest existential threat contemporarily. If we fail to curb greenhouse gas emissions from the use of fossil fuels, the implications of rising global temperatures will include widespread agricultural and fisheries failure, the extinction of hundreds of thousands of species, and the destruction of entire ecosystems (Lindwall, 2022).

How much worse will the problem get?

Emissions* and expected warming by 2100

*Emissions are in Gigatonnes of CO2 equivalent

Source: Climate Action Tracker

BBC

Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-46384067>

According to this graphical representation, if countries fail to address this problem and do not act appropriately, the problem will get much worse in the upcoming years. Climate scientists have modified their concept of what they consider to be the "secure" threshold of climate change in recent years. For many years, scientists have advocated that the global temperature rise must be kept beneath 2 degrees Celsius by the end of the century to prevent the worst consequences. Countries who signed the Paris Accord promised to retain temperatures well below 2 degrees Celsius above the level of pre-industrial times and to pursue efforts to limit the temperature increase even further to 1.5 degrees Celsius. However, experts increasingly believe that we must limit temperature increases to less than 1.5 degrees Celsius (Climate change: Where we are in seven charts and what you can do to help, 2020).

Among these countries which need to retain their temperatures and limit their human activities, the following are some prominent names that are significantly contributing in the emission of greenhouse gasses.

The world's top emitters of carbon dioxide

Megatonnes of CO2 per year

Note: One megatonne = 1,000,000 tonnes

Source: EC, Emissions Database for Global Atmospheric Research, 2018 data

Source: <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-46384067>

Moreover, analyzing the effects of climate change in the world, (Climate Action - United Nations, 2023) highlighted some noteworthy effects of climate change posing threat to every living being on this planet. These effects include,

- Higher temperature
- Violent storms
- Feminine upsurge
- Threat to food security
- Poverty and deportation

Considering these effects, countries have been striving hard to cope with the challenges posed by climate change. But among all these challenges, the threat to food security ranks at the top as it has been threatening the lives of millions of people, giving rise to a number of health diseases, and escalating the ratio of poverty.

The causes of the global rise in hunger and inadequate nutrition include environmental

alterations and a spike in extreme weather occurrences. Livestock, crops, and fisheries might all be lost or become less productive. The marine resources that sustain billions of people are under threat due to the ocean's increasing acidity. Food sources from hunting, fishing, and herding have been interrupted in many Arctic locations due to changes in snow and ice cover. Heat exhaustion can reduce the amount of water and grasslands available for foraging, which can lower agricultural production and have an impact on cattle (Climate Action - United Nations, 2023).

Inextricable linkage between Climate change and Food Security

Food security and climate change are closely related, with the former posing serious risks to the latter. Extreme weather events such as heatwaves, floods, and famine are becoming more often and severe as the planet's weather patterns change. The cessation of agricultural practices results in lower crop yields and a decrease in the total manufacturing of food. Changes in temperature and rainfall patterns can also make some areas more inappropriate for farming or change the emergence of seasons, making it more difficult for farmers to raise conventional crops. Climate change-related water shortage makes the problem worse and affects agricultural and irrigation requirements (McCracken, 2023).

Crop susceptibility is increased by the spread of alien species, diseases, and pests brought on by changing weather. Together, these variables cause disruptions in the availability, cost-effectiveness, and distribution of food, which can result in food scarcity, unstable prices, and inadequate nutrition, particularly in communities that are already at risk. Therefore, to protect food security, climate change must be addressed through sustainable farming methods, water management plans, and international initiatives meant to lessen the effects of climate change on food production and delivery networks (McCracken, 2023)

Bearing this interconnectedness in mind, it will not be wrong to assert that food security, an effect of climate change, has been intricately intertwined to it, posing serious threats to people's health in the form of threatening nutrition and water quality. Nutrition and health are intimately connected to

food security. Conventional wisdom links food security to people's ability to obtain food. Nonetheless, the stability of food availability is at risk due to various factors such as the expansion of urban areas, unequal distribution of income, excessive population growth, environmental decline, the well-being of animals, and the quality of food. Another crucial element in maintaining a nutritious diet is guaranteeing the purity and authenticity of the food we consume.

Programs to ensure food safety and protect against food contamination are essential parts of any food security plan (Middleton, J., et al, 2020). The hunger of the 1980s has been replaced with food security or insecurity. In order to guarantee that every individual has consistent access to an ample supply of nourishing food to support an active and well-balanced lifestyle, we need to focus on two key aspects:

- Ensuring that individuals can obtain food that meets their personal preferences in a way that aligns with societal norms,
- Enhancing the efficiency in obtaining food that is both nutritionally suitable and safe.

There is a problem of food insecurity when access to adequate nutrition is restricted or uncertain. The qualitative, quantitative, psychological, as well as social, or normative elements relevant to food insecurity are measured at the household or individual level and are qualified by their involuntary nature and periodicity. The means by which a family obtains food is a potential contributor to food-insecurity.

Most of the food in countries that aren't very well off comes from small farms. Changes in the climate and changes in the weather are making their lives harder. Recent food problems around the world have shown how weak globalized food systems are. They also demonstrated that climate change is one of many environmental, demographic, social, as well as economic factors that add to instability and lack of food security,

Problems with health & quality of life might arise as a result of hunger and malnutrition brought on by food insecurity. Food security or insecurity indicators are important for understanding the nutritional status of people, communities, and nations (Béné, C., 2020).

Over the next few decades, feeding society may become increasingly difficult. Food production has long been a key tool to reduce food poverty. In 2010, even though the world produced a sufficient amount of food to feed the global population, a staggering 925 million individuals remained vulnerable to hunger. As a result of global environmental change (GEC), satisfying future demand will be challenging. This thesis makes the case for studying complicated food security/GEC issues from a systems perspective.

The objectives encompass two main aspects:

- I. Establishing a framework to facilitate meaningful discussions focused on improving food security and involving a diverse range of stakeholders and interested parties.

- II. Incorporating comprehensive analyses of all aspects of food security, including production, storage, processing, packaging, trading, and consumption, while considering the various dimensions of food security, including access, utilization, availability, and their respective components (Fujimori, S., et al, 2019).

This indicates that nutrition should be integrated into all four dimensions of food security i.e.,

which affects poorer groups in marginal environments in addition to other groups. It's better to take a look at these modifications as a whole than to try to find individual causes.

Issues and Threats to Pakistan

As a matter of fact, climate change has become one of a key issue of our contemporary age. Being the first to observe its early warning signs,

we also have the final chance to stop it before it unfolds. Ignorance will only get us so far. The world is filled with examples of animal extinction, melting glaciers, increasing sea levels, harsh weather, and more already.

Due to the unfolding of this phenomenon, a number of countries are now exposed to climate change disasters, and emerging nations are at far higher risk. South Asia has become increasingly vulnerable to disasters as a result of this grave issue, which is having a negative influence on the region particularly Pakistan (ahsan, 2022).

Due to its geographical location, Pakistan has been facing the disastrous effects of climate change more strongly from the last 20 years. As a result of which, from the last 20 years, Pakistan has been continually placed in the top 10 most risk prone nations on the Climate Risk Index, with 10,000 casualties from disasters caused by climate change and \$4 billion in monetary damages from 173 events of very severe weather.

Such challenges and issues pose the risk of igniting disputes over finite resources like water brought on by the effects of climate change. Natural disasters brought on by climate change, such as heat waves, floods, or tsunamis, can further heighten tensions between populations who have previously experienced conflict (Siddiqui, 2022).

Evaluating the issues being caused by climate change to Pakistan, it came forward that due to rise in temperature, rainfall intensity and sea level, following threats and issues are being posed to Pakistan. They include issues of,

- ❖ Shortage of Water Resources
- ❖ Agricultural sector
- ❖ Health risks
- ❖ Forests Destruction
- ❖ Coastal regions

According to a study, Pakistan encounters "substantially more extreme temperatures than the worldwide average, via a potential rise of 1.3°C-4.9°C by the year 2090s over the 1986-2005 starting point," as well as some of the greatest risk of catastrophe instances in the world, positioned 18 out of 191 countries by the 2020 Inform Risk Index."

Moreover, the most favorable emitting scenarios predict a 3.7°C rise in world average temperature by 2080-1999. In addition, shifts in Pakistan's hydrologic systems, and therefore its water supply, are little unclear, despite the fact that prolonged droughts are anticipated to become more prevalent. Extreme weather events are predicted are going to become more frequent and extreme, increasing the likelihood of disaster, especially for less fortunate and minority communities (Climate Action - United Nations, 2023).

Pakistan typically had some of the highest scorching temperatures in the globe, with an average monthly maximum of about 27°C and an average June maximum of 36°C. In Pakistan, there is presently a 3 percent chance on average every year that an extreme heat wave would occur in any given location. A sizable portion of society is in risk, as evidenced by statistics that during Pakistan's 2015 scorching temperatures, over 65,000 people were hospitalized due to heatstroke (ahsan, Climate Change and its impacts in Pakistan, 2022).

Major health repercussions can arise when weather patterns combine to cause extended periods of heatwave, as is the case in many parts of Pakistan where annual temperatures reach 38°C or more. Pakistan experienced 126 heatwaves between years 1997 and 2015, a yearly average of seven, with an accelerating tendency. Being a low-middle-income country, Pakistan has an agrarian economy. Although with the passage of time, progress has been made and Pakistan has become industrialized enough that one-third of its population is enjoying a healthy lifestyle in cities (ahsan, Climate Change and its impacts in Pakistan, 2022).

The nation heavily depends on its climate-sensitive water, soil, and forest assets for food and nutrition security. 42% of people still work in the agriculture sector, making it a prominent employment. Approximately ninety percent of agriculture is irrigated by water from the glacier-fed River Indus and its tributaries. Climate change has caused glacier melt to intensify, which raises the possibility of glacier reservoir gushing floods (GLOF) and landslides

downward. The inability of individuals to work and support themselves will be impacted by a number of factors, including heat exhaustion, malnutrition, the spread of diseases transmitted by insects like dengue fever, and a rise in the prevalence of aquatic infections (Lindwall, 2022).

Food Security of Pakistan

When it comes to Pakistan, extreme weather has become the norm in Pakistan over the last few years. The annual chronic nature of heat waves, droughts, and torrents has an impact on the security of food and water. The impoverished, older people, and women are examples of disadvantaged groups that bear the brunt of these repercussions the most. Moreover, Pakistan is among the top ten countries most vulnerable to extreme climatic events, while being one of the carbon emitters with the lowest emissions worldwide (malik, 2022).

Substantially affecting the access to food for people, the recent flood of 2022 in Pakistan further wreaked mayhem on crops making the situation worst. Pakistan is now experiencing a serious food crisis as a result of the floods particularly of 2022. An aggregate of 78,000 square kilometres (30,000 square miles) of crops were inundated across 81 regions. It is estimated that over eighty percent of the country's crops were devastated.

Among of the worst-affected provinces is Sindh, which provides a significant amount of the country's food. Sindh's destruction and loss of agricultural land and damage to crops have infuriated farmer organizations such as the Hari Welfare Association and the Sindh Abadgar board. They claim that floods caused damage to more than 15 million people, especially farmers and agricultural laborers who make their living from agriculture on daily basis (malik r. , 2023). Destroyed were food crops that formerly covered thousands of acres, including rice, onions, tomatoes, and numerous other vegetables. The more than 6000km (3,728 miles) of highways and bridges that have been destroyed have significantly hindered the transportation of the food that had survived. Pakistan is further predicted to experience yield reductions

in numerous essential agricultural and commercial crops, including wheat, cotton, sugarcane, maize, and rice during the time period of next ten years, according to estimates in the World Bank's 2021 Climate Risk Country Profile (malik r. , 2023).

Therefore, long-term obstacles to physical food access may result from climate change, and these obstacles may also translate into financial barriers to food security. These effects of climate change happened in a country where inflation was already on the rise and had reached a 14-year high of almost 25 percent in July prior to the floods.

The Pakistan Bureau of Statistics stated that the cost of necessities has increased by 44% as a result of climate change. As per the World Bank study entitled "Country Climate and Development," there might be a 4.7 percent increase in Pakistan's poverty rate. It implies that 9 million more people are falling into poverty. The combination of rising rates of poverty and high inflation is likely to provide significant obstacles to people's ability to afford food, so impeding Pakistan's efforts to ensure adequate nutrition.

It is considered imperative to keep employing the newest technologies for farm mechanization jobs including irrigation, crop production, protecting crops, and land expansion in order to increase manufacturing. Maintaining reasonable costs for farm supplies, such as high-yielding cultivars, and promoting the advancement of affordable farm machinery and supplies powered by renewable energy sources as an alternative to extremely costly fuel that harms the environment can both greatly improve agriculture (tahir, 2022).

As a matter of fact, Pakistan ranks among the countries having higher population. Pakistan's expanding population presents a significant food concern. Acute food scarcity affects 18% of Pakistanis, out of 43% who are food insecure, according to the World Food Programme. Pakistan's rural employment and food needs are largely met by agriculture. Its performance is still reliant on the weather, though. Climate variation has an impact on agricultural production, which raises the level of food

insecurity and has an impact on Pakistan's export industry.

Having all this in mind, one might argue that, in principle, food security is a crucial component of resource planning as a whole, but there is no evidence of this at all in reality. How the authorities handled the recent unusual monsoon deluge is a clear illustration of their failure to fulfill their obligations in addressing the destruction caused by heavy rain in different parts of Pakistan, particularly the most affected areas of Sindh and Balochistan (mahesar, 2022).

Literature Review

Climatic changes have a significant impact on food security, affecting various aspects of agricultural productivity, crop yields, and overall food production. Numerous studies and research have investigated this relationship, highlighting the consequences of climate change on global food systems (Mukhopadhyay, R., et al, 2021). Climatic factors, such as extreme weather events, shifts in temperature and precipitation patterns, and changing growing seasons, can disrupt agricultural productivity. Extreme weather events like droughts, floods, storms, and heatwaves have become more frequent and intense, leading to significant crop losses.

These events can destroy crops, erode soil quality, and affect the availability of water for irrigation, ultimately reducing agricultural productivity (Leisner, C. , 2020). Changes in temperature and precipitation patterns can directly influence crop yields. Higher temperatures can accelerate the rate of evaporation, increase water stress for plants, and negatively impact photosynthesis and crop development. Additionally, altered rainfall patterns can lead to water scarcity or excess moisture, both of which can harm crop growth. These conditions can lower crop yields, reduce the nutritional quality of food, and limit overall food production (Kogo, B. K., 2021).

According to my analysis based on the findings of the above-mentioned scholars, reduced agricultural yields, weakened food quality, and a limited ability for total food production are the cumulative effects of these climate changes, without any doubt. The complex relationship that exists between agricultural productivity and

climate change highlights the pressing need for proactive policies, robust farming methods, and adaptive techniques to lessen the potentially disastrous effects on global food security.

Climate change can cause shifts in the timing and length of growing seasons. Changes in temperature and precipitation patterns can affect the onset of spring and the arrival of rainfall, which are critical for planting and crop growth. As these patterns shift, farmers may face challenges in adapting their planting and harvesting schedules accordingly. Such shifts can disrupt the synchronization between crop growth and local climatic conditions, leading to decreased yields and reduced food availability (Molotoks, A., Smith, P., and Dawson, T. , 2021).

The impact of climatic changes on food security extends beyond agricultural production. Climate-induced food insecurity affects various dimensions, including access, availability, and affordability of food. Climate change can disrupt transportation systems, making it difficult to deliver food from production areas to markets. Extreme weather events can damage infrastructure, such as roads and bridges, hindering the movement of food. In rural areas, where communities rely on subsistence farming, climate change can reduce their ability to produce enough food for themselves, leading to increased reliance on external aid (Fujimori, S., et al, 2019).

It is very true that Climate change affects agriculture in many ways and has significant consequences for food security. Farmers are challenged to modify planting and reaping schedules in response to changes in temperature and rainfall patterns during the period of growth, which lowers yields and decreases the amount of food available. Climate-related food insecurity affects not just agricultural output but also food availability, pricing, and access.

The transfer of food from manufacturing regions to markets is hampered by infrastructure for transportation damage caused by extreme weather events. Subsistence-farming rural populations are particularly vulnerable, becoming less self-sufficient in food and more dependent on outside assistance. To address

these issues and safeguard food systems from the growing risks posed by climate change, comprehensive methods combining robust infrastructure, egalitarian policies, and adaptable agricultural techniques must be implemented.

Reduced crop yields and production instability can result in food shortages. Climate change-induced extreme weather events can destroy entire harvests, leading to reduced availability of food in affected regions. This can increase competition for limited resources, potentially triggering conflicts and displacements.

Climate change can affect food affordability due to increased production costs, market volatility, and decreased supply. Lower crop yields can drive up prices, making food less affordable for vulnerable populations. Additionally, changing climatic conditions can force farmers to adopt costly adaptation strategies, such as investing in irrigation systems or drought-resistant crops, further impacting the cost of food production (Wiebe, K., 2019).

According to (Interactive country fiches, 2025) Pakistan is one of the ten nations in the world most impacted by natural catastrophes and climate change. Over the last century, the country's average annual temperature has increased by around 0.63°C, and the sea level along the Karachi coast has risen by about 1.1 mm annually. However, the sea level is said to have risen at a pace of 3.6 millimeters year between 2006 and 2015. Precipitation patterns in Pakistan have historically been complicated. Annual rainfall declined for a long time in the early 20th century, but since 1960, there has been a minor increase. Nonetheless, significant sub-national diversity is concealed by this general trend. For example, Pakistan's coastal belt and arid plains have seen a 10%–15% drop in mean rainfall since 1960, which has contributed to the continuous deterioration of the nation's mangrove and wetland ecosystems [5]. At the same time, Pakistan has seen a rise in both the number of hot days annually and the frequency of heavy rainfall events.

According to the facts mentioned by (Supreme court of Pakistan, 2024) , depending on the emissions scenario, Pakistan's annual mean temperature is predicted to increase by roughly

3°C to 6°C by the end of the century. The low-lying coastal regions south of Karachi towards Keti Bander and the Indus River delta are probably going to be impacted by the anticipated 60 cm rise in sea level, which would also contribute to soil salinization and coastal erosion. It is anticipated that average annual rainfall will show significant inter-annual fluctuation but not a major long-term trend. Extreme weather events are also predicted to become more often and intense in Pakistan, which will have a negative effect on the nation's natural and human resources.

It is widely acknowledged that Pakistan is extremely vulnerable to climate change. Extreme climate events like floods, droughts, cyclones, heavy rainstorms, and extremely high temperatures have already become more frequent and intense in Pakistan due to rising temperatures, affecting the nation's ecosystems, inhabitants, infrastructure, and settlements. The World Bank Group estimates that between 1992 and 2021, weather-and climate-related disasters in Pakistan caused property, crop, and animal damage totaling US\$29.3 billion (inflation-adjusted to 2021 US dollars), or 11.1% of 2020 GDP. Flooding is expected to affect more people in Pakistan as a result of climate change; by 2035–2044, there will probably be around 5 million more people exposed to extreme river floods, and by 2070–2100, there may be about 1 million more people exposed to coastal flooding yearly (Supreme court of Pakistan, 2024).

One of the major troubles caused by climate change is the threat to food security. Where hunger and malnutrition in Pakistan have been increasing. Clearing the notion of food security, (Malik, 2023) stated when everyone, everywhere, has physical and financial access to enough safe, nourishing food that satisfies their dietary needs and food choices for an active and healthy life, that is known as food security. Climate change has had a significant impact on Pakistan's physical food access. Crops in Pakistan have been severely damaged by the latest flood. As a result of the floods, Pakistan is currently facing a serious food crisis. In 81 districts, a total of 78,000 square kilometres (30,000 square miles) of crops were inundated. Over 80% of the

country's crops are thought to have suffered damage. A significant amount of the country's food is produced in Sindh, one of the hardest-hit provinces. Farmers' groups including the Sindh Abadgar board and the Hari Welfare Association are furious over Sindh's crop destruction and loss of agricultural land.

They claim that over 15 million people, including farmers and other regularly employed agricultural workers, have suffered as a result of floods. Thousands of hectares of food crops, including rice, onions, tomatoes, and other vegetables, had been damaged. The devastation of the more than 6000km (3,728 miles) of roads and bridges has caused significant disruptions in the transportation of the food that has survived. The World Bank's 2021 Climate Risk Country Profile projects that over the next ten years, Pakistan would see "yield decreases in numerous essential food and cash crops, including cotton, wheat, sugarcane, maize, and rice (malik r. , 2023).

The Pakistan Bureau of Statistics reported that climate change has caused a 44% increase in the cost of necessities. The World Bank's Country Climate and Development study suggests that Pakistan's poverty rate could rise by 4.7%. It indicates that 9 million more individuals are falling into poverty. High inflation and rising poverty will make it extremely difficult for people to afford food, which will make it more difficult to guarantee nutritional security in Pakistan. The Global Hunger Index now places Pakistan at number 92 out of 116 countries. Prior to the floods, 38 million people—mostly women and children—were suffering from moderate to severe food insecurity, with most of them going to bed hungry. According to WHO estimates, 18% of Pakistani children suffer from clinical undernutrition (Baron & Asad, 2023).

Moreover, the demographic groups most affected are older women and children. They will bear the brunt of this disaster. At least 33 million people, both in rural and urban regions, have been directly affected by the floods. More than 70% of respondents in the Khyber Pakhtunkhwa province said they had difficulty obtaining much less nutrient-rich food, according to a september research by the

International Rescue Committee (IRC) and its partners. According to UN estimates, the flood caused an economic loss of \$40 billion. Other provinces are not in a better position than this one. Thus, Pakistan's food security is under long-term risk from climate change. A nation like Pakistan has a sizable population and an agro-economy. Because agriculture is so important to its economy, it cannot afford to be disrupted. Both short-term and long-term policies should be made by the government. The government should focus its short-term efforts on draining floodwaters from rural agricultural sites so that winter crops may be planted there. By doing this, the country won't face a long-term food security problem (Baron & Asad, 2023).

To meet the growing nutritional demands of a rapidly expanding population, humanity has expanded agricultural land, increased crop production, and engaged in global agricultural trade. However, the effects of climate change will impact agricultural output, food supplies, and global markets. To examine the changes in the global agricultural trade network based on two greenhousegas emissions scenarios, we have integrated seven Gridded Crop Models and five Earth System Models with a dynamic global economic model. A few locations control much of the agricultural market when CO2 levels are high. More regions would engage in international trade if carbon emissions were reduced. Distributed networks are more resilient to environmental and societal changes (Syed, A., and Eash, N., 2022).

Strategic Policy Options for Sustainable Resilience of Pakistan:

In order to resolve these socio-economic consequences of climate change and food security in Pakistan, the development of sustainable resilience requires smart policy options. These regulations need to be all-encompassing, inclusive, and flexible, addressing both short-term issues and long-term objectives. These policies revolves around,

Climate Resilient Farming Practices

- Encourage climate-smart farming by using crop varieties that can withstand heat and drought.
- Promote crop diversification and teach farmers water-saving irrigation methods, such as sprinkler and drip systems.

Improving the Management of Water Resources

- Update irrigation systems and encourage the use of technology like drip irrigation and laser land leveling.
- To alleviate water scarcity, install rainfall gathering systems and replenish groundwater.

Disaster Risk Reduction

- Bolster flood, drought, and extreme weather early warning systems.
- To lessen the effects of disasters, invest in climate-resilient infrastructure, such as flood defenses and resilient roads.

Sustainable Land Use and Forestry

- To repair damaged ecosystems, expand afforestation initiatives like the "10 Billion Tree Tsunami."
- Encourage sustainable land management techniques to counteract desertification and soil erosion.

Public Awareness

- Organise workshops and awareness campaigns about sustainable farming and climate adaptation.
- Engage local communities and youth in climate action projects to increase resilience at the grassroots level.
- Encourage effective resource usage (such as trash reduction and water conservation) by launching national awareness campaigns.

Methodology

This research opts the **Qualitative research method** to build and justify its arguments. Because qualitative research is a type of research methodology that plays a significant role in providing an in-depth analysis and understanding of the particular problem via different strategies. Among these knowing about the knowledge, discernments, and understanding of the people concerning to the problem remains at the top. Furthermore, qualitative research revolves around the cosmos of,

These are all attained from the partisanship and life experiences of participants involved in the research. In short, the methodology "qualitative research" is frequently used to refer to a wide variety of research approaches with various epistemological presumptions and aim to explore the answers of the research questions reinforced by philosophy, procedure and methods (mohajan, 2018).

Research Design

This research paper further opts 'Case Study' and 'Content Analysis' as a research design of the Qualitative research methodology.

Referring to **Case Study**, it is that type of research design that contributes in providing a comprehensive study of a particular issue or person or any cluster, place or occasion. Not only does it offer tangible, circumstantial, and in-depth information about the particular subjects, but also allows the researcher to reconnoiter the crucial features, meanings and insinuations of the case chosen (Combes, 2019). Following this interpretation, this research study has chosen the case studies of two neighboring countries i.e., India and Pakistan to compare analyse the implications of Climate change on the food security of both countries and how their administrations have been handling it.

The second research design i.e., **Content Analysis** extensively used to analyse a particular content containing the presence of words, themes and meanings. It is a type of research design which contributes in enumerating the qualitative information or data at a larger scale by cataloguing the data and linking distinctive smithereens of information to prepare a useful summary. Furthermore, to be more precise, this research study employed the relational content analysis because relational content analysis is quite different from other types of content analysis.

This is due to the fact that relational content analysis goes beyond concepts and meanings. It seeks to explore the relation between those concepts and meanings. Similarly, in this research study the mere focus is on the phenomenon of climate change and food security in India and Pakistan. Employing this content analysis, this research paper explored the relation between climate change and food security stating that both are directly related to each other (What is Relational Content Analysis in Qualitative Research? Step-by-Step Guide, 2023).

Research Approach

In order to meet the required goals and objectives, this research paper employed the **interpretivist research approach**. The foundation of

interpretivism is the idea that the real world is arbitrary, complex, and socially produced. That signifies that we can only comprehend another individual's reality by their own perspective of it. This experience or perspective may be distinct from another individual's and influenced by the latter's historical or social context.

Data Collection Technique

Being qualitative in nature, the data collection technique used for this research study is **Document Analysis**. Document analysis is one of those data collecting method in qualitative research which studies the existing human interactions or their writings in the form of websites, articles and laws. Based on this analysis, the researcher can make deductions out of it based on the parameters of the desired research (Document Analysis Method of Data Collection, 2012). Therefore, while conducting the document analysis for this research, the reports and records published by the officials of both states concerning to the steps being taken by them to counter the threat of climate change on food security has been evaluated. Furthermore, few of the data has been extracted from the authentic articles and websites also.

Analysis & Discussion

Analysis:

Climate change poses serious threats to Pakistan's food security, including water scarcity, unpredictable rainfall, extreme weather events, and rising temperatures. These elements jeopardize the availability of vital resources and impair agricultural output, especially for staple crops like wheat. The country's agrarian viability is further threatened by water scarcity, which is made worse by ineffective irrigation and disagreements with India under the Indus Waters Treaty. The devastating floods of 2022 brought to light Pakistan's food systems' susceptibility, resulting in extensive damage, price spikes, starvation, and unstable economies. Migration brought on by climate change has increased the strain on urban resources and infrastructure, creating more social and economic problems. Pakistan must take a comprehensive approach to addressing these concerns, concentrating on

disaster preparedness, climate-resilient agriculture, sustainable water management, and collaboration with the international community on common issues. Consequently, Pakistan can protect its population from the worsening consequences of climate change and ensure food security by prioritizing cooperation, strengthening policies, and promoting resilience.

Discussion:

The article critically evaluates the socioeconomic repercussions of climate change on food security in Pakistan, demonstrating the intricate relationship between climate change, food production, and sustainable development. Pakistan has tremendous challenges due to rising temperatures, changed rainfall patterns, and catastrophic weather events, such as the 2022 floods, which damaged crops, infrastructure, and livelihoods, resulting to food shortages and surging prices. Water scarcity exacerbates food security, while mismanagement of resources and inadequate agricultural potential impede self-sufficiency. The research underlines the critical need for coordinated policies focusing on climate adaptation, sustainable resource management, and inclusive governance to alleviate these dangers. Recognizing the impact of commerce, technology, and international cooperation, the report calls for resilience-building approaches to provide equitable access to nutritious food amidst climate difficulties.

Conclusion

The research highlights the socioeconomic ramifications of climate change while examining its complex effects on Pakistan's food security. Millions of livelihoods are at risk due to the loss in agricultural output brought on by rising temperatures, unpredictable rainfall, and frequent extreme weather events. The disproportionate impact on marginalized groups and small-scale farmers exacerbates destitution, disparity, and rural-to-urban migration. The research emphasizes how climate change and food security are intertwined, highlighting how extreme weather affects food availability, affordability, and nutrition. Pakistan is one of the top 10 nations most at risk from climate change, even though it

contributes very little to global emissions. Important problems that worsen food poverty include water scarcity, agricultural losses, health concerns, and growing inflation.

Pakistan's food system is in terrible shape, as seen by recent events like the devastating floods of 2022, which devastated 80% of crops and impacted millions of people. Inflation, poverty, and poor governance in the face of climate-related calamities exacerbate the issue. To lessen these difficulties, the study promotes an integrated framework of policy responses. Crop diversification and climate-resilient agriculture are the main medium-term initiatives, while catastrophe risk reduction and food assistance are the short-term ones. Land-use changes, climate-smart agriculture, and regional cooperation are key components of long-term solutions. In order to create a sustainable and just food system in Pakistan, the report urges utilizing international climate money and cultivating international collaborations.

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